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LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

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TO DEFINE IS TO KNOW

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Abstract

Educators are immediately aware of the linguistic, literacy, and workplace or course material challenges that LESLLA learners face. Less readily apparent are the challenges such learners face when encountering school-based tasks and their associated ways of thinking. Because familiarity with such tasks and ways of thinking are built from an early age in formal education, teachers frequently do not realize that the tasks themselves, as well as the ways of thinking, are bewildering to LESLLA learners. To take one example, when a teacher or standardized test question asks in one form or another, “What is X?”, learners are expected to provide salient characteristics, functions, and categories appropriate to the given term or concept. However, questions that ask for explicit definitions are not common in informal settings. LESLLA learners come from backgrounds of informal learning and often struggle to engage in age-appropriate formal education. Thus, school-based tasks and ways of thinking, such as defining, are largely unfamiliar to them and must be explicitly taught, just like language and emergent literacy skills. In this paper, we explore how to do so, using the teaching of defining as an extended example. Once LESLLA learners have developed this skill, they can apply it across classroom, workplace training and, licensing preparation settings, all of which require them to define terms and concepts specific to their training or course work.

LESLLA learners have been receiving growing attention over the last decade or so (e.g., Kurvers, 2015; Pettitt & Tarone, 2015; Shapiro, Farrelly, & Curry, 2018). Nevertheless, research-based recommendations for effective pedagogy remain minimal. In addition, most research on pedagogical practices has focused on two major areas: (1) developing LESLLA learners' alphabetic print literacy skills, as found, for instance, in the annual proceedings published by LESLLA; and (2) developing work-related content knowledge in tandem with proficiency in the language of the host country (e.g., Thomas & Grünhage-Monetti, 2019). As this paper illustrates, there is another key avenue for inquiry that has been overlooked.

When educators encounter LESLLA learners, they quickly realize the linguistic, literacy, and workplace challenges that these learners face. Less readily apparent are the challenges LESLLA learners face when attempting to engage in school-based tasks and their associated ways of thinking. These constitute new habits of mind for LESLLA learners, habits that are developed through full participation in Western-style formal education (Berry et al., 2011; Flynn, 2007; Gauvain & Munroe, 2009).

Background

We have argued previously in our work that these decontextualized, school-based tasks and associated ways of thinking are a major hurdle LESLLA learners confront in formal classrooms and in training settings that prepare them for certifying or qualifying for vocational professions (DeCapua, Marshall, & Tang, 2020; DeCapua, 2018; DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013). The structured development of print literacy and participation in formal education develops certain types of cognitive pathways (Cole, 2005; Deheane, 2013; Gauvain et al., 2011), or “academic ways of thinking.” These ways of thinking are essential to classroom success and are becoming increasingly pervasive in the 21st century workplace as well as in everyday, contemporary life (Duran & Şendağ, 2012; Parrish & Johnson, 2010). Because familiarity with such tasks and academic ways of thinking are built from an early age in formal education, teachers frequently do not realize that the tasks as well as the ways of thinking are bewildering to LESLLA learners.

What do we mean when we talk about decontextualized school-based tasks and associated ways of thinking? These tasks range from highly structured, close-ended questions, such as multiple choice or fill-in-the-blank, to less structured open-ended ones, such as short answer questions or prompts or table completion (DeCapua, Marshall, & Tang, 2020). In essence, decontextualized school tasks are literacy-based tasks with associated academic ways of thinking that in the classroom are expected to build and demonstrate knowledge. They require specific habits of mind to organize and present information and the ability to think abstractly versus based on personal experience and concrete facts in students' lives (Abadzi, 2003). The tasks, the surface manifestation of academic ways of thinking, demand literacy beyond basic decoding skills; instead these tasks require the ability to interpret the two-dimensional world of print and representation as well as the ability to present information and knowledge in specific prescribed ways.

Although empirical studies are limited, one study of an A2 (Common European Framework) level class of LESLLA learners revealed that, despite extensive pre-practice, learners still had difficulty understanding the culminating task, not because of a lack of language proficiency or alphabetic literacy skills, but because the task required a way of thinking, namely abstraction, that LESLLA learners were unused to (DeCapua & Triulzi, in press).

Scaffolds suggested to help learners are often in and of themselves part of this hidden challenge. Typically, visuals are considered a valuable aid in language learning. Yet, drawings themselves require the ability to interpret abstract representations of the real world. When LESLLA learners are given worksheets with drawings, they often have no idea what the drawings are supposed to represent because they have not developed the ability to understand representational text, even those which can be regarded as “culture neutral” (Cornwall, 1992; Hvitfeldt, 1985). Altherr Flores (2017), for instance, found that the clip art drawing of a pen on a worksheet was variously interpreted by the learners as either a fish or insect, or not at all, in instances where the learners responded that they didn't know what the drawing represented.

Likewise, in many widely-used language textbook series (e.g., *Ventures* by Cambridge), drawings are used not to represent the object itself, but to be a placeholder for another object – an iconic

representation – which can cause another layer of confusion, as noted by Altherr Flores (2017). For example, a teacher who participated in the authors’ professional development, recounted to the other participants how some of his students did not know what a stamp, postage or post office were. Yet in the textbook the students were using, they were expected to do a language exercise based on reading maps of places in an imaginary neighborhood where the picture of a stamp was meant to illustrate a post office and the picture of a shopping cart, a supermarket. The students were asked about the locations of these buildings with no other information to help them relate the images to the buildings they stood for. These textbook visuals are supposedly iconic images and drawings, yet these representations of buildings, places, and activities are not necessarily recognizable to LESLLA learners, similar to the findings in Altherr Flores’ study (2017). Overall, evidence indicates that these semiotic symbols and drawings are likely to be misinterpreted by those with emergent print literacy, irrespective of native language or new language proficiency (Arbuckle, 2004; Dowse & Ehlers, 2003). Visual representations, in so far as they are not photos, are abstract interpretations of the real world, and like an alphabet or other form of writing, must be learned.

Another widely used type of scaffolding, graphic organizers, are visual displays that show relationships between information, ideas, and concepts. For example, if an activity is to evaluate similarities and differences, the teacher may begin by having learners complete Venn Diagrams. This type of graphic organizer consists of two intersecting circles. In one side of one circle, learners enter the similarities; in the other side of the second circle, learners enter the differences. Where the two circles intersect, the learners enter information applicable to both items being examined. The decontextualized task is completing Venn Diagrams and the associated academic way of thinking is comparison and contrast. Graphic organizers such as a Venn Diagram are not intuitive, but rather schematic educational tools that students, beginning in elementary school, learn to make sense of and use to organize a specific way of thinking associated with any given type of graphic organizer.

Other graphic organizers may require learners to complete tables, circles, or boxes – the decontextualized tasks – according to certain characteristics. Food, for instance, can be classified as salty, sweet, or

sour; tools by function, indoor or outdoor, hand or electric. In this case, the associated way of thinking is scientific classification according to specific attributes (Flynn, 2007). This is the same academic way of thinking that leads those with age-appropriate formal education to differentiate mammals from reptiles or fiction from non-fiction.

These examples underscore the difficulties LESLLA learners have in accessing knowledge and information in Western-style formal educational and workplace training settings. They must learn to abstract and distance themselves from personal lived experiences and the three-dimensional real world to knowledge based on different ways of understanding and interpreting the world and to the two-dimensional world of print and visual representations.

Theoretical Underpinnings

In this paper, we explore how to teach decontextualized tasks and ways of thinking, using the skill of defining as an extended example.

Research on child first language acquisition informs us on concept development and its relationship to defining. When babies first encounter a “bottle,” it is a “baby bottle.” As babies see other types of bottles, such as water bottles, wine bottles, or medicine bottles, they may not identify them as bottles because they are not “their” bottles. Conversely, there is an early tendency to see all containers for liquids, such as jugs or covered mugs, as “bottles,” even when they are not members of that category. Over time, young children intuit the concept of bottle and the specific types of bottles, one of which is a baby bottle, and more specifically, their individual bottles. This intuitive grasp of categories occurs gradually so that concept formation around “bottle” grows. Once children enter Western-style formal educational settings, these concepts become formalized as part of the process of schooling. The development of semantic categorizations occurs through such classroom procedures as explicitly defined new concepts in textbooks and teacher-student question answer sessions, including the most common classroom question, “What is a/an X?” (Keil, 1989; Litowitz, 1977; Marinellie, 2010; Walker, 2002). Over time, in school, students learn the technique of defining through participation in a variety of literacy and language development activities, such as reading increasingly challenging texts and looking up definitions for words they do not know and reflecting on and applying

appropriate dictionary definitions (Benelli et al., 2006; Snow, 1990). Acquiring vocabulary in the real world is highly based on context and experience as opposed to formally defined vocabulary learned in school that follows a prescribed formula, i.e., the classic dictionary definition of a word.

For LESLLA learners, this transition from informal learning and concept formation to a more formal approach of explicitly defining an object has not necessarily taken place, so that the seemingly simple question, “What is a bottle?” may elicit questioning stares, pointing to a bottle in the immediate environs, or, perhaps an explanation of what a bottle is used for. Those who have participated in age-appropriate Western-style formal education will understand that the teacher is asking for characteristics that describe what a bottle is as opposed to something that would not be considered a bottle. LESLLA learners will not have had the benefit of activities leading to the ability to define words and will, for the most part, demonstrate intuitive understanding but be unable to articulate the type of facts required in a formal definition.

A common classroom activity is matching a vocabulary word or picture with the correct definition. On the one hand, this is a language and early print literacy activity requiring learners to recognize a word and its meaning. However, when learners must not merely match but produce their own definition or use their understanding of the definition to do something with words, more than memorization is required. From the perspective of LESLLA learners, who have primarily experienced informal ways of learning, it would be sufficient to memorize the dictionary definition, give an example, or simply point to the object in order to define it. In Western-style formal school settings, on the other hand, when learners must define a word, they are expected to know and be able to provide salient characteristics, functions, and categories appropriate to the given term or concept (Marshall & DeCapua, 2013). Compare, for instance, three learner responses to this question:

What is a tree?

Learner 1: “A **tree** is a tall, woody plant with roots, a trunk, branches and leaves that can live for many years.”

Learner 2: “Tree for make house, fire.”

Learner 3: (Stands up, walks to the window, points, and says) “That tree.”

Only Learner 1’s response would be considered acceptable in a school setting because it is a dictionary-like, scientific definition. Learner 2’s response, while not inaccurate, is unacceptable in formal educational settings, where students are taught to distinguish between formal, scientific versus functional or everyday definitions (Webb, 2009). Learner 3 has misinterpreted the task as one of identification or comprehension of vocabulary, rather than one of defining.

On standardized tests, including licensing exams, similar types of questions can be found, and test-takers must either choose or provide the definition, again based on the same criteria. These criteria, i.e., characteristics, functions, and categories, entail an abstract conceptualization of the world. Such a conceptualization is based on reason, utilizing specific types of logical, rational, scientific ways of thinking grounded in observable and generalizable facts from which the individual and personal experience are removed and generally discounted or seen as invalid or extraneous (Brownie et al., 2015; Flynn, 2007). This is at variance with the habits of mind LESLLA learners have developed through their prior experiences with informal ways of learning rather than through Western-style formal education and extensive print literacy development (Cole & Packer, 2016).

The key differentiating factor in the sample learner responses to the question, “What is X?” is the concept of decontextualization. LESLLA learners, when they do provide a definition, seek to place the term into some meaningful context and relate it to their experience. The example above about using wood from a tree to build a fire, is such a definition. Formal education requires the opposite, in other words, responses that are decontextualized from life. “Correct” responses must align with prevailing modes of abstraction and logical modes of thinking. The term must be removed from context in order to grasp its (universal) essence. These two ways of approaching the act of defining are contradictory. LESLLA learners hoping to succeed in formal educational or workplace training settings must learn to remove themselves and their lived experiences in the real world to accept the prevailing norms of abstraction and decontextualization.

This challenge is a “hidden challenge.” Many educators are not aware that LESLLA learners’ difficulties making progress may well stem from the nature of the tasks and associated ways of thinking themselves. Even those who become aware do not necessarily realize

that these, like language, emergent print literacy skills, and content or work knowledge, must be explicitly taught. Here we show how LESLLA learners can be guided through the process of making their intuitive understanding become the foundation for formulating definitions using school-based ways of thinking and academic language required for constructing formal definitions.

Teaching Tip

One useful technique for helping LESLLA learners make the transition to producing formal definitions is the Collections Project. Here the class amasses many examples of the same item, each very different in many minor respects, but each nonetheless belonging to the larger classification into which the item falls (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011). By seeing all of the items in the “collection,” the class can begin to conceptualize what it would mean to compose a description of the item in its prototypical form that would then apply to each and every individual iteration in their class’s collection. One class of LESLLA learners collected plants. As one might imagine, they varied greatly in size, material, function, and other characteristics, but were all, of course, the same type of item – plants.

In this technique, which also serves to develop relevant and meaningful vocabulary, the learners as a whole class share words that can be used to describe the various items. In one version of this activity, each learner has one plant and individually describes it, or alternatively partners can do this together. Some of the words are specific to the individual plant, while others may apply to all plants. In this way, learners begin to see what will be used for the formal definition. For example, words to describe size will not be relevant since plants come in all sizes; however, words that describe leaves would include every item in the collection since nearly all plants have these, and therefore would become part of the definition.

As in teaching any new procedure, the teacher can break this activity down into steps. The four steps to follow in constructing a definition are:

Guidelines for Building Definitions for Nouns

STEP ONE

The basic sentence frame that the class learns to define nouns is:

A/An _____ (the item in the collection) is a _____ (in which the second blank refers to a category) with _____ (characteristics common to all of the items).

STEP TWO

A slightly more difficult version replaces “with” (a prepositional phrase) by “that has” (a relative clause)

A _____ (the item in the collection) is a _____ (in which the second blank refers to a category) that has _____ (characteristics common to all of the items).

For the plant collection, the learners work with their teacher to define a plant as follows:

A plant is a living thing with a stem, leaves or flowers, and roots.

A plant is a living thing that has a stem, leaves or flowers, and roots.

STEP THREE

The teacher chooses a post-nominal structure and posts the sentence frame

- Prepositional phrase “*with...*”
- Relative clause “*that...*”

A more complex sentence frame includes a more advanced relative clause as the post-modifier of the noun, thereby introducing more information.

A plant is a living thing with a stem, leaves or flowers, and roots, *that grows in the ground and needs sun and water to survive.*

STEP FOUR

As they become more familiar with the concept of categories, the learners analyze the collection of plants and compose definitions of individual plants. In such this case, for instance, the definition begins this way:

A/An _____ is a plant with/that has...

Now the learners supply the specific characteristics of the plant they have from the class collection. Examples:

- My plant is a kalanchoe. A kalanchoe is a short, tropical plant with a long stem, thick, wide green leaves, and small groups of flowers.
- My plant is ivy. Ivy is a climbing evergreen plant with shiny, green, five- pointed leaves.
- My plant is a daisy. A daisy is a small plant with flowers that have a yellow middle and white petals.

Expansion Activities

Collections can be used in many additional ways to build LESLLA learners' emergent print literacy skills, language, content, and ways of thinking.

Adjective Word Order (in English)

For one, the learners' definitions can become part of lessons on adjective word order, so that LESLLA learners know which adjectives to put first, next, and so on. The order of adjectives can be taught and placed on a teacher or student-made poster for the classroom:

1. Opinion
2. Size
3. Shape
4. Condition
5. Age
6. Color
7. Origin (*where from*)
8. Material (*made of*)
9. Function (*used for*)

Since LESLLA learners must develop new habits of mind, as a next step, the class collection can be used to practice comparing and contrasting, a new way of thinking. The collection itself provides a realistic context for LESLLA learners to practice this new way of thinking. Working with a partner for example, they examine ways in which their individual plants are similar and/or different. Then, by rotating partners, the learners will have other responses as they compare and contrast different plants from the collection. As this activity unfolds, the teacher provides the typical vocabulary and syntactic structures that accompany comparison and contrast, ranging from the most basic to the more complex. (See DeCapua, Marshall, & Tang, 2020, for a discussion of the language of comparison/contrast.)

Mystery Bag

Another activity that can be used to introduce defining is the Mystery Bag Activity, discussed in detail in DeCapua & Marshall, 2011. In this activity, each learner receives one item in a closed paper bag. Only that learner can open and look at what is inside while initially keeping the item hidden from the rest of the class. In every bag, there is an item that is shaped like an apple (or any other object) but that is not actually that item and has an everyday function, such as a basket, candle, soap, magnet. Only later in the activity do the learners realize that all the items share an essential characteristic, i.e., representing an apple, but that each item has a significantly different function. The idea is to build the concept of abstraction as learners develop defining skills. Since each object represents an "apple," yet is not an apple, this activity helps LESLLA learners understand how objects may be similar in representation but nevertheless be different in that each item has a separate function. This activity becomes even more engaging if one student has the actual item in the mystery bag as a surprise, such as a real apple, when everyone reveals what is inside the mystery bag.

This activity can lead to describing the objects with sentence frames, such as:

My apple is a/an magnet.

It is _____, _____ and _____. (predicate adjectives)

It is a/an _____, _____, _____ magnet. (prenominal adjectives)

Learners can practice using both predicate adjectives and pronominal adjectives, again, referring to the poster on Adjective Word Order. They can expand their vocabulary as they identify the distinguishing features of their individual, apple-shaped object.

Once learners have completed lessons on defining as part of their English instruction, they will be better prepared for providing definitions in their other classes or in preparing for taking licensing exams. Having developed this skill, they can apply it across learning settings. The most useful type of definition is the one for nouns, as discussed here, as it is the most commonly occurring in classrooms. However, a similar unit can be included that expands defining into activities and sentence frames for other parts of speech.

Semantic Feature Analysis

A more challenging activity is to introduce Semantic Feature Analysis (See Table 1: Plant Characteristics). This will expose LESLLA learners to the type of classification that is common in Western-style formal education and workplace training settings, where they are preparing for qualification or licensure exams. In this activity, learners identify the distinguishing features of the various plants in the class collection and specify whether or not a given plant has that particular feature. This is yet another way to define. In this case, the learners must engage in analysis and then place the results of that analysis onto a table, which is itself a decontextualized way of looking at the plant collection.

Table 1

Plant Characteristics

NAME OF PLANT	TROPICAL?	FLOWERS?	SUCCULENT?	LEAVES?
Kalanchoe	YES	YES	YES	YES
Ivy	NO	NO	NO	YES
Daisy	NO	YES	NO	YES

(See Marshall & DeCapua, 2013 for more on semantic feature analysis.)

Discussion

The key to teaching school-based ways of thinking and introducing and practicing decontextualized tasks is to use meaningful context. The Collections Project does this by avoiding traditional lessons on defining or comparison/contrast and substituting an experiential approach that is hands-on, concrete, and collaborative, and therefore familiar to LESLLA learners. At the same time, this approach fosters their transition to Western-style formal learning settings. Because in such settings, “to define is to know,” we have focused on this most basic of skills to highlight the need for instruction in school-based tasks and academic ways of thinking.

In implementing these activities, it is important to begin with items that are already familiar to the learner, so that they can focus on learning how to define, how to describe precisely, and how to compare and contrast similar items. Although the plants they collect in their classroom may be unfamiliar to them, they are very likely familiar with plants from their home country, and the project could include photos and videos of their native plants. They can even produce a theme booklet with plants from their home countries with detailed descriptions and definitions of each type of plant. (See Marshall & DeCapua, 2013, for a detailed explanation of Theme Booklets).

While the many commercially available materials for LESLLA learners understandably focus on language and content instruction, it is equally important for these learners to develop a deep understanding and comfortable familiarity with the type of thinking and the kinds of activities and learning tasks that are conducted in Western-style formal educational and many workplace training settings. Although non-LESLLA language learners, with age-appropriate prior education and deep experience in formal ways of learning, will also find differences in the system of education and formal workplace training in their new country, they will more easily make the transition than will LESLLA learners who must make a major leap to form new habits of mind. Until there are materials that address this hidden curriculum directly, teachers will need to develop projects, such as the Collections Project, to teach LESLLA learners this often-neglected material so essential to their ultimate success in any program where they are attempting to demonstrate new mastery of English, content, and skills knowledge.

The Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm® (MALP®)

The Collections Project presented here follows the guidelines of an instructional model developed for LESLLA learners that can be used to generate additional projects that focus on the formal schemata of school, i.e., familiarity with decontextualized tasks and associated school-based ways of thinking (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013). The Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm (MALP) takes the learning paradigm of LESLLA learners and juxtaposes it with the learning paradigm that is generally assumed and expected in most Western-style educational and workplace training settings. Then, selected features of each paradigm are combined to create a mutually adaptive paradigm that recognizes the priorities for learning of LESLLA learners, while at the same time recognizes the necessities of the classroom and workplace training, so that LESLLA learners can experience success. Figure 1 shows how MALP draws from both paradigms. MALP accepts learners' conditions for learning, namely, for the material to be immediately relevant to learners and for the activities to foster interconnectedness among the learners and with the teacher. MALP combines processes for learning from both paradigms, so that both the LESLLA learners' cultural norm of sharing of responsibility and the teacher's need to ensure individual accountability are honored. Lastly, as discussed here in detail, MALP focuses on new tasks and new ways of thinking, but with activities that incorporate familiar language and content, so that any new schemata will be accompanied by familiar schemata as a support for learning.

Figure 1
Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm (DeCapua, Marshall, & Tang, 2020; DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013)

Based on this new paradigm, teachers can use the MALP Teacher Planning Checklist to analyze their projects and see how they include all the elements of MALP. Figure 2 shows the filled-in checklist for the Collections Project.

Figure 2
MALP Teacher Planning Checklist (DeCapua, Marshall, & Tang, 2020; DeCapua & Marshall, 2011; Marshall & DeCapua, 2013)

MALP Teacher Planning Checklist®
available at www.malpeducation.com

A. Accept Conditions for Learning
<p>A1. I am making this lesson/project immediately relevant to my students' lives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The collection item itself – a plant – is something familiar to them. • Learners may have owned, seen, or used plants like those in the collection.
<p>A2. I am helping students develop and maintain interconnectedness with each other.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners and teacher learn more about each other's interests, likes and dislikes. • Learners can learn how to refer to the plants in each other's languages.
B. Combine Processes for Learning
<p>B1. I am incorporating both shared responsibility and individual accountability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class collectively creates sentences from sentence frames. • Pairs work together to generate additional sentences. • Each person adds information related to own object. • Learners write their sentences in their notebooks.
<p>B2. I am scaffolding the written word through oral interaction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners share answers to questions about the objects orally. • The teacher writes their descriptive words – object characteristics – on the board. • The teacher elicits information about their objects and writes this on the board. • Learners read sentences back orally and later write them in their notebooks.
C. Focus on New Activities for Learning
<p>C1. I am developing school-based ways of thinking using familiar language and content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activity is making the abstract – classification – concrete, by using real-world objects. • Learners use translanguaging, nonverbal communication, and sentence frames as linguistic scaffolds. • The familiarity of the collection objects provides content scaffolding.
<p>C2. I am teaching learners how to engage in decontextualized tasks to demonstrate their mastery of these new ways of thinking.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners write formal definitions of nouns using both prenominal and postnominal structures. • Learners represent information in abstract visual formats, such as tables.

Using MALP, teachers can supplement their regular curriculum with projects that develop LESLLA learners' ability to thrive in Western-style formal educational and workplace training settings. These projects complement and enhance their emergent print literacy development, their language proficiency, and the content they are

learning in their programs. Without this essential instruction in decontextualized tasks and associated school-based ways of thinking, LESLLA learners will have more difficulty and take a longer time to master new knowledge and develop essential classroom and workplace skills. This extended example of defining has provided a template for teachers seeking to implement MALP for other projects. To define is to know, but that is just the beginning. The pathway to success continues.

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